

Research Article

Interactive PnP Innovation For Muamalat Diploma Students' Final Year Project

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Abstract: The Scientific paper is a required subject for final year Muamalat Diploma students at UiTMCTKD in semester 5. The Wheel of Fortune Interactive PnP Innovation Project (PWofKi) method is used to assess students' comprehension of input for writing a scientific paper or research paper that was given in the form of a lecture during a scientific paper writing workshop held prior to students registering for this subject. This strategy was developed to encourage students to be more enthusiastic about comprehending all of the critical procedures involved in producing scientific articles without becoming bored, stiff, or passive in response to the feedback provided. The employment of (PWofKi), which employs an intriguing gaming method, can be studied as a teaching and learning mechanism (PnP) in promoting learning delight. As a result, the goal of this study is to assess students' understanding of the appropriateness of using PWofKi in the PnP process for the subject of Scientific Papers (IMU304), as well as to pique students' interest in the subject of Scientific Papers (IMU304), in order to improve the learning and teaching environment. A questionnaire was provided to 57 participants in a pilot research. To assess students' perceptions of implementation, data was analysed using SPSS 24 and compared to the mean score (PWofKi). The results show that the mean score is 4.26 on a 5-point scale. This suggests that the innovation of usage (PWofKi) in PnP topic IMU 304 can solve the problem of boredom while also making students have fun and improving their knowledge of the learning delivered. One of the games that may be used to interact and communicate for learning goals is the PWofKi technique. The study's findings indicate that the PWofKi method is a novel strategy in the IMU304 PnP process that can be used by any students pursuing Diploma, Degree, Masters, or Doctorate degrees in any public or private higher education institution.

Keywords: Wheel of fortune, Scientific Papers, teaching and learning, research.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, one of the most significant developments in higher education has been the rise of interactive learning as a learning medium. It has become a popular method for independent learners

to gain new knowledge and abilities (Milligan & Littlejohn, 2017). Interactive learning is a structured set of learning activities and resources that are web-based, usually free of charge, and may be accessed by hundreds of people at the same time (Azevedo & Marques, 2017). However, several studies have discovered that, despite the fact that interactive learning enrollment rates can be startlingly high, completion rates are typically disappointingly low (Azevedo & Marques, 2017), and learning online without professional tutor support forces learners to self-motivate (Milligan & Littlejohn, 2017). Other recent research, however, discovered that interactive learning is a reliable platform that can deliver independent and flexible learning experiences to Malaysian higher education students, particularly during COVID-19 (Safri, Mohd & Hanafiah, 2020),

As a result, the purpose of this study is to investigate the potential of interactive learning for Scientific Papers, as designed by the researchers, in boosting students' literacy on Interactive learning, engaging students in meaningful learning, and increasing their drive to learn. Thus, the goal of this study is to assess students' knowledge of the appropriateness of employing an interactive learning process for scientific articles, as well as to pique students' attention, so that the learning and teaching environment becomes more motivating and enjoyable.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Research Design

As a result of the fact that the purpose of this study is to determine whether or not the interactive learning approach is effective for teaching the IMU304 course that is provided by UiTM Terengganu, the methodology utilized in this study is regarded as a quantitative one and utilizes a descriptive research design.

2.2 Population and Sample

Students from UiTM Terengganu make up the sample for this study's population. On the other hand, the students from UiTM Terengganu who are registering for the IMU304 class are the ones who will be included in this study's target sample. According to the recommendations made by Roscoe (1975), sample sizes for most types of study should be between 30 and 500.

2.3 Sampling Technique

As the current situation is still unpredicted due to the COVID-19 pandemic, a snowball sampling technique was used whereby an online structured questionnaire was developed using Google Forms, with a consent form appended to it. The link of the questionnaire was sent through a WhatsApp and Telegram application and spread among the UiTM Terengganu students especially Diploma in Muamalat programme groups who were advised to circulate it in their community. The participants were encouraged to forward the survey to as many targeted participants as possible. On receiving and clicking the link, the participants will be auto-directed to the information about the study and informed consent. After accepting to take the survey, they filled in the demographic details, and then answered a set of questions provided.

It can be seen that 57 students responded to the questionnaire circulated. It fulfills the rule of thumb as proposed by Roscoe (1975), for which sample sizes larger than 30 and less than 500 are appropriate for most research.

2.4 *Data Collection*

Participants who have specific characteristics, with access to the internet, could participate in the study. All the information individual responses were kept confidential, and they were told about the purpose of this investigation.

2.5 *Data Analysis*

Data collected using questionnaires from 57 respondents were analyzed descriptively using Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS) 24 with reference to mean scores to measure students' perceptions of the implementation of the interactive learning for the IMU304 course.

2.6 *Research Design*

The game design started with some PWoFKi game tools. Among them are a game rule book, a mini Wheel of Fortune, 16 envelopes, 16 question test cards (various colors), 16 answer cards (various colors) and stars as a reward for questions that can be answered well. This can make the game more interesting and fun. It uses high quality art paper material card material. This game adapted from Wheel of fortune is expected to open minds and motivate students to deepen their knowledge related to research. PWoFKi is a new initiative to make it easier for students to learn in a relaxed way with the concept of gamification and fun education that is more interactive and efficient.

3. **FINDINGS**

There were a total of 57 students took part in this survey, and the allocation of those participants into their respective genders is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Numbers of Students Based on Gender

Gender	Numbers (n)	Percent (%)
Male	20	35.1
Female	37	64.9
Total	57	100

The results of the study are presented in table 1, and it can be seen that there are a total of 20 male students (35.1%), while there are 37 female students (64.9%).

Table 2: Mean Score of Each Items

No	Items	Min Score
1	Sharing ideas through PWoFKi	4.21
2	Collaborative Learning with PWoFKi	4.19
3	Learning is more interesting with PWoFKi	4.28
4	Fun activities with PWoFKi	4.34

5	More effective learning with PWoFKi	4.25
6	The use of PWoFKi helps to better understand the topic being taught	4.28
7	The use of PWoFKi interests me to focus more in pnp sessions	4.19
8	PWoFKi keeps me and all students active in pnp sessions	4.28
9	PWoFKi is very suitable for adaptation in pnp	4.26
10	This PWoFKi is a pnp innovation that is very beneficial for students	4.32
	Total	4.26

n=57

Table 3 presents the level of interpretation that should be applied to the mean value. This perception's explanation is founded on Oxford's (1990) understanding of the phenomenon. The level of interpretation of perception was low for mean values in the range of 1.00 to 2.49, while mean values in the range of 2.5 to 3.49 indicated a moderate level of perception interpretation. The mean value falls somewhere between 3.5 and 5.00, according to the interpretations of high and good perception.

Table 3: Min Value and dan Interpretation Perception

Min Value	Interpretation Perception
1.0 to 2.49	Low
2.5 to 3.49	Moderate
3.5 to 5.00	High

Thus, with a mean score of 4.26, which demonstrates a high mean score value, this indicates that the interactive learning course IMU304 has a considerable impact on students as a medium of Teaching and Learning (PnP).

4. DISCUSSION

In today's world, there is no way to get around the necessity of incorporating information and communication technology into the teaching and learning process within the realm of education. However, lecturers face a big challenge when it comes to optimising its use as a daily teaching practise. This is because a low degree of self-efficacy with technology makes it difficult to make the necessary alterations in the teaching process. This circumstance cannot be refuted because, according to Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1977), each individual will not exhibit the same level of performance because the challenges that each individual must face vary depending on the field and the task. Consequently, each individual will not demonstrate the same level of performance.

Figure 1: User Manual of PWOFKi Interactive Learning Games

Figure 2: Gaming Instructions

PWOFKi is a new approach in the PnP process for the IMU304 code. It is also able to overcome the problem of boredom, in fact students feel more fun and it is proven to increase their understanding of the learning delivered compared to the approach of only providing input online (Raja Yusof, R.N.A., Nik Yaacob, N.R., 2022). The PWOFKi method is also one of the new games that can be applied in all PnPs that require students to collaborate and communicate with each other to create two-way learning. It is also a new game that has its own novel and unique features based on the concept of gamification and educational entertainment that is more interactive and efficient.

Learning through games such as PWoFKi can indirectly motivate students because it has elements of fantasy, challenge and can encourage curiosity among students. This game is very effective in learning based on two main factors which are interactive and attract students' attention. Thus, it can also create a happy learning atmosphere (Jaffar, M. N., Ab Rahman, A., Zakaria, M. A., Yeap, M. J. M. F., & Shakor, M. F. A.,2020). Therefore, it can indirectly reduce the level of stress among university students to prepare their special Scientific Papers as well as for all students whether at the Diploma, Degree, Masters and Doctorate degrees in all public or private higher education institutions.

This burst of creativity is expected to be monetized by developing a complete PWoFKi kit in an appealing design, material, and colour, as well as cards with input connected to research writing. Furthermore, the researcher's goal is to share ideas with other teachers so that they might be implemented in PnP. When students' interest and understanding of courses connected to Scientific Papers for the IMU304 code are raised through game innovation, the effectiveness of this PnP may be shown (PWoFKi).

5. CONCLUSION

In summary, this method definitely manages to attract more students passionate about understanding all the important processes in the Scientific Papers course. Scientifically they are without feeling bored, rigid, or passive to that input given. This approach can be analyzed as a mechanism for teaching and learning (PnP) in driving the fun of the process of learning carried out.

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References

- Abou El-Seoud, S.; Seddiek, N.; Taj-Eddin, I.; Ghenghesh, P.; Nosseir, A.; El-Khouly, M. (2014). E-Learning and Students' Motivation: A Research Study on the Effect of E-Learning on Higher Education. *Int. J. Emerg. Technol. Learn*, 9, 689–695.
- Ali, N. R. N. (2020). Kaedah Permainan Bahasa Dalam Pengajaran Dan Pembelajaran Bahasa Arab [The Method Of Language Game In Teaching And Learning Arabic]. *Al-QIYAM International Social Science and Humanities Journal*, 3(3), 60-66.
- Azevedo, J., & Marques, M. M. (2017). MOOC success factors: Proposal of an analysis framework. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Innovations in Practice*, 16, 233-251. Retrieved from <http://www.informingscience.org/Publications/3861>
- Aziz, A. (2018). Evaluating the Design Standard of UiTM Massive Open Online Courses. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies*, 6 (4).
- Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*, 84(2),191-215.
- Coman, C., Tîru, L. G., Mesesan-Schmitz, L., Stanciu, C. & Bularca, C. (2020). Online Teaching and Learning in Higher Education during the Coronavirus Pandemic: Students' Perspective. *Sustainability*, 12, 10367; doi:10.3390/su122410367
- Demirci Cavide. 2017. The Effect of Active Learning Approach on Attitudes of 7th Grade Students. *International Journal of Instruction*, 10(4), 129-144.
- Harris, C. (2009). Meet The New School Board: Board Games Are Back – And They're Exactly What Your Curriculum Needs. *School Library Journal*, 55, 24-26.

Hsiao, H. S., Chang, C. S., Lin, C. Y., & Hu, P. M. (2014). Development of children's creativity and manual skills within digital game-based learning environment. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 30(4), 377-395. doi:org/10.1111/jcal.12057.

i-Learn Centre (2016). Garis panduan pembangunan e-kandungan kursus UiTM. Retrieved from http://i-learn.uitm.edu.my/v2/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/Buku_Garis_Panduan.pdf.

Jaffar, M. N., Ab Rahman, A., Zakaria, M. A., Yeap, M. J. M. F., & Shakor, M. F. A. (2020). Tahap Keberkesanan Gamifikasi Global Halal Game (GHG) Dalam Kalangan Peserta Program Halal Eksekutif Profesional. *International Journal of Islamic and Civilizational Studies*, 7(3), 45-58.

Jasmi K.A., M. F. (2011). Amalan Penggunaan Bahan Bantu Mengajar dalam Kalangan Guru Cemerlang Pendidikan Islam Sekolah Menengah di Malaysia. *Journal of Islamic and Arabic Education*, 3(1): 59-74.

Katelyn M. Cooper, Virginia R. Downing & Sara E. Brownell. (2018). The Influence of Active Learning Practices on Student anxiety in Large-enrollment College Science Classrooms. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 5(23), 1-18

Lessard, J.J., (1998). Adolescent Stress an Workload: From Bamboo Seed to Flying. *Guidance & Counseling Journal*,14, 15-19.

Mackenty, B. (2006). All Play And No Work. *School Library Journal*, 52, 46-48.

Mahat, H., Arshad, S., Saleh, Y., Aiyub, K., Hashim, M., & Nayan, N. (2020). Penggunaan dan penerimaan bahan bantu mengajar multimedia terhadap keberkesanan pembelajaran Geografi (The use and acceptance of multimedia teaching aids on the effectiveness of Geography learning). *Geografia-Malaysian Journal of Society and Space*, 16(3).

Mancha, R., & Shankaranarayan, G. (2020). Making a digital innovator: Antecedents of innovativeness with digital technologies. *Information Technology & People*, 34(1), 318-335.

Milligan, C. & Littlejohn, A. (2017). Why Study on a MOOC? The Motives of Students and Professionals. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 18 (2)

Norfarahi Zulkifli, Mohd Isa Hamzah & Khadijah Abdul Razak. (2020). Isu dan cabaran penggunaan MOOC dalam proses pengajaran dan pembelajaran. *Journal of Research, Policy & Practice of Teachers & Teacher Education*, 10 (1), 77-94.

Oxford, R.L. (1990). *Language Learning Strategies: What Every Teacher should Know*. Boston: Heinle & Heinle Publishers.

Raja Yusof, R.N.A., Nik Yaacob, N.R. (2022). Level of Self-Efficacy in Applying Information and Communication Technology for Teaching and Learning among Islamic Education Teachers in Secondary Schools in Penang. *Asian People Journal*, 5(1), 179-189.

Safri, S.N.W., Mohi, Z. & Hanafiah, M.H. (2020). Massive Open Online Course (MOOC): Our saviour during COVID-19 pandemic? *Journal of Tourism, Hospitality & Culinary Arts*, 12(3), 120-128.